

Research Article

From Vernacular Traditions to Sustainable Innovation: Behavioral and Spatial Adaptations in Batak Simalungun Urban Houses

JF Bobby Saragih¹

¹ Architecture Department, Faculty of Engineering, Binus University, Indonesia

*Corresponding author: bsaragih@binus.edu

Abstract

This study aims to identify behavioral and spatial strategies that enable houses to function dually as private domains and communal social spaces. The research focuses on the transformation of Batak Simalungun houses—represented through the residence of Tuan Amborokan and its continuity in the second generation—from vernacular forms toward sustainable urban adaptations. Employing a qualitative ethnographic approach, including participatory observation, in-depth interviews with elders, and visual documentation, the study explores how Simalungun dwellings negotiate urban land constraints while maintaining cultural and social values. The findings reveal that spatial flexibility, the use of movable furniture, and the design of adaptable open areas allow houses to serve simultaneously as domestic dwellings and collective interaction spaces, thereby reinforcing customary practices, solidarity, and community cohesion. These findings highlight that such behavioral and spatial strategies embody vernacular architectural principles—namely, ecological adaptation, strengthening social networks, and preserving cultural identity—which have been reinterpreted within a modern urban context. Accordingly, this study offers conceptual contributions for architects, planners, and policymakers in integrating vernacular wisdom into contemporary housing design, while also advancing the goals of SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities.

Keywords: vernacular; sustainable ; behavior ; adaptation ; simalungun

“...Our house has a spacious yard—quite large and distinct from the surrounding houses, with a special room at the front that functions as an office ...”
(LS, Tuan Amborokan’s daughter, 85 years old)

“...in addition to the office space, our house was equipped with four bedrooms, two kitchens, and a fairly large family room... the bedrooms were arranged in a row on the right side of the building... There was a separate bathroom located between bedroom number 1 and bedroom number 2...”
(LS, Tuan Amborokan’s daughter, 85 years old)

“...the house was able to accommodate a considerable number of children and several wives..”
(LS, Tuan Amborokan’s daughter, 85 years old)

“...he family room is quite spacious... and sometimes it is used as a sleeping area for the grown (adult) sons... There are bars/grilles on each window...”
(LS, Tuan Amborokan’s daughter, 85 years old)

“...whereas the workers’ houses were located relatively farther away from our house “
(LS, Tuan Amborokan’s daughter, 85 years old)

Sustainable Innovation: Behavioral and Spatial Adaptations of Simalungun Batak Houses in Urban Areas

Figure 2. Plan of The Saragih Family at Medan City (Source: Author, 2025)

Sustainable Innovation: Spatial Flexibility

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. (a) Open Layout: Spatial Flexibility in the Saragih Family house ; (b) The spatial arrangement is organized according to the principle of *Tolu Sahundulan* (Source: Author, 2025)

Sustainable Innovation: Movable Furniture

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. (a) The Saragih Family house with movable furniture ; (b) The Saragih Family house without furniture in the guest & family room (Source: Author, 2025)

Sustainable Innovation: adaptable open areas

Figure 4. The adaptability of the shop's function into a venue for traditional ceremonies in the Saragih family house (Source: Author, 2025)